

Observation of ultrametricity in photonic spin glasses

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Physical Sciences - Article

Keywords: Spin Glass, Ultrametricity, Replica Symmetry Breaking, Random Laser

Posted Date: January 8th, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5433512/v1>

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Additional Declarations: There is **NO** Competing Interest.

1 Observation of ultrametricity in photonic spin
2 glasses

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17 **Abstract**

18 Hierarchy is the architecture of complex systems [1]. While Euclidean metric
19 describes homogeneous and static systems, ultrametric geometry is for heteroge-
20 neous ensembles, hierarchic relations and dynamic contexts. Applications spread
21 across all fields: communication technologies, information retrieval, clusterwise
22 regression, analysis and synthesis of narratives and emotions [2].

23 The paradigmatic model describing complex systems is the spin glass theory,
24 according to which the topology of the many metastable energy states is intrinsi-
25 cally ultrametric, as a consequence of the breaking of their symmetry [3]. Despite
26 the importance, a real experimental observation of the universal behaviour has
27 not yet been reported, due to the difficulty of finding a physical system that dis-
28 plays all the characteristics of spin glasses.

29 Random lasers have recently been proposed as excellent photonic counterparts
30 of spin glasses with robust replica symmetry breaking features [4–6].

31 Here, we report the ultrametric structure of the replica space with clustered
32 domains in random lasers, as predicted in the Parisi Ansatz [7]. We show that

33 the number of the states forming isosceles triangles in the metric space increases
34 through the laser threshold giving rise to the construction of a genealogical tree.
35 Moreover, from the hierarchical topology of the states we obtain a direct obser-
36 vation of the complex energy landscape with evident breaking of ergodicity in
37 the glassy regime. Our results, as well as being a milestone in complexity sci-
38 ence, fuel the lively research into physical systems which in recent years has been
39 leading to the creation of optical computers and quantum annealers [8–12].

40 **Keywords:** Spin Glass, Ultrametricity, Replica Symmetry Breaking, Random Laser

41 Ultrametricity is a mathematical concept that dates back to the late nineteenth cen-
42 tury with the introduction of the topology of the so-called p-adic numbers[13]. The
43 basic concept is: given three points A, B, C the distance d between them obeys
44 the ultrametric triangular inequality $d(A, C) \leq \max\{d(A, B), d(B, C)\}$. This inequal-
45 ity is stronger than the triangular one describing the usual metric of Archimedean
46 space $d(A, C) \leq \{d(A, B) + d(B, C)\}$. In the ultrametric space all triangles are either
47 equilateral or isosceles with the third side shorter than the two equal ones [13].

48 The ultrametric topology is typical of hierarchical trees. For this reason, ultra-
49 metricity first appeared in taxonomy [14]. The evolutionary relationships of biological
50 species relying on their genetic features is a phylogenetic tree, which shows the history
51 of connections of species, or taxa [15].

52 Besides biological classification, ultrametricity came into dataset analysis in the
53 1960s. It has a central and powerful role in the evaluation of big data clusterabil-
54 ity, a topic extremely relevant in deep and complex neural networks within machine
55 learning [16].

56 In physics, ultrametricity made its entry in the mean-field theory of spin glasses
57 (SGs), which is the fundamental theory of order-to-disorder transitions [17]. In spin
58 glasses the coexistence of disorder and frustration is responsible of a complex energy
59 landscape, with many metastable minima that are pure states of the out-of-equilibrium
60 system. These states have been identified as replicas, meaning identical copies of
61 the same disordered system [18]. In the low-temperature SG phase, the existence of
62 infinitely many pure thermodynamic states coincides with the breaking of the replica
63 symmetry and hierarchy appears.

64 The overlap matrix $q_{\alpha\beta}$ of replica states measures their degree of similarity. In the
65 glassy regime $q_{\alpha\beta}$ assumes fluctuating values with a non trivial shaped probability
66 distribution, which signals the ergodicity breaking in the thermodynamic limit [18].
67 The Nobel prize Giorgio Parisi proposed an exceptional and elegant Ansatz for the
68 overlap matrix, which breaks the global permutation symmetry between replicas and
69 captures the physics of the many pure states [7].

70 Mézard et al. [3] demonstrated that the topology of the space of the pure states or
71 replicas is intrinsically ultrametric, as a consequence of randomness and of the laws of
72 large numbers. In the proposed genealogical tree the end points represent states and
73 the branches clusters. The distance between two end points is defined as the number
74 of generations one has to go back in order to find a common ancestor.

75 In this picture a succession of phase transitions is represented by the branching
76 points. The clusters of low-temperature glassy states become the states of the system
77 at a higher temperature.

78 By numerical methods, the ultrametric structure of the energy states in SGs has
79 been widely proved in agreement with all the known analytical results [19–21].

80 However, so far, the experimental demonstration is lacking. Recently, several con-
81 cepts related to SG theory have been successfully applied in the field of random
82 photonics [22], specifically for random lasers (RLs) [4, 23–27], and nonlinear waves [28].
83 The experiments provide direct access to the complex configuration of the replicas
84 and their fluctuations. For the first time and after 40 years, the distribution of the
85 Parisi overlap $q_{\alpha\beta}$ has been obtained from random laser measurements and Replica
86 Symmetry Breaking (RSB) has been experimentally proven [4].

87 Here we demonstrate the ultrametric structure of the RL overlap matrix that
88 emerges above the laser threshold when the system enters in the glassy regime. We
89 report the progressive clustering through the order-disorder transition reproducing
90 experimentally the Parisi Ansatz formulated for spin glasses [3, 7]. The related dendro-
91 gram evidences the hierarchical topology of the observed replicas proving the predicted
92 universal behaviour in the SG theory.

93 In addition, from the complex ultrametric structure of the overlap matrix we achieve
94 the first experimental observation of the energy landscape with evident breaking of
95 ergodicity in the RL glassy phase.

96 At variance with previous works, we demonstrate RSB by using overlap graphs
97 instead of the overlap probability distributions and we evidence the unambiguous
98 equivalence of the two strategies in detailing the laser phase transition.

99 RSB from overlap graphs

100 Random Lasers (RLs) [29–32] are laser sources where the optical feedback for stimu-
101 lated emission is the multiple scattering of light. RLs differ from conventional lasers
102 with defined cavities. Our RL is a compact Rhodamine 6G doped silica powder fabri-
103 cated by a conventional Sol-Gel synthesis at room temperature. Details on fabrication
104 and standard characterization are reported in Methods.

105 The RL complex material has a broad fluorescence emission centered at 590 nm at
106 low pumping and incoherent laser emission when increasing pumping above threshold.
107 The transition to the laser regime at 0.5 mJ is evidenced by intense fluence and
108 spectral narrowing, as shown in Methods section.

109 When the stimulated emission occurs, we observe significant spectral fluctuations
110 (Fig 7b-c of Methods) from one laser shot to another under identical conditions. In
111 the framework of the SG theory, each spectrum is a different configuration of the
112 same system with quenched disorder, *i.e.* a replica. In each replica, a large number of
113 electromagnetic modes coexist and their interaction grows by increasing the injected
114 energy. At high pumping, modes compete in energy similarly to magnetic spins at low
115 temperature.

Fig. 1 Graph representation of the Replica Symmetry Breaking. **a**, Random laser at low pumping and in the paramagnetic regime and at high pumping with replica symmetry breaking in spin glass regime. Our RL is made of dyed powder pumped by an external green laser and with red emission. **b-d**, Graphs with connection between 100 replicas when varying the pumping energy. Edges connect states with overlap $|q| \geq 0.5$. **e**, Connectivity number K (black squares) and $|q_{max}|$ (red circles) versus pumping energy. The RSB threshold 0.5 mJ is defined for $|q_{max}| = 0.5$ and the saturation of K .

116 The mode energy at wavelength λ is given by the spectral intensity $I(\lambda)$ [4, 33, 34].

117 The Parisi overlap $q_{\alpha\beta}$ between two replicas α and β is

$$q_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\sum_{\lambda=1}^N \Delta_{\alpha}(\lambda) \Delta_{\beta}(\lambda)}{\sqrt{(\sum_{\lambda=1}^N \Delta_{\alpha}^2(\lambda)) (\sum_{\lambda=1}^N \Delta_{\beta}^2(\lambda))}}. \quad (1)$$

118 In equation (1) the variation

$$\Delta_\alpha(\lambda) = I_\alpha(\lambda) - \bar{I}(\lambda) \quad (2)$$

119 is, for a replica α , the difference between each spin $I(\lambda)$ and the average value $\bar{I}(\lambda) =$
120 $1/N_s \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_s} I_\alpha(\lambda)$, calculated over N_s replicas (spectra).

121 The overlap matrix $q_{\alpha\beta}$ is the correlation between the fluctuations of replica pairs.
122 When the replica fluctuations become uncorrelated and lose their similarity the system
123 enters into a glassy disordered regime. Such replica symmetry breaking is evidenced
124 by a non trivial shaped probability distribution of the overlap (Fig. 1a and Fig. 7e-f
125 in Methods).

126 Here we give evidence that the RSB transition is observed in network graphs
127 measured from the RL spectra.

128 Figures 1b-d show a set of 100 points randomly distributed in a spherical geometry.
129 They represent 100 replicas, i. e. single shot measurements, obtained at the identical
130 pumping energy. Each displayed edge is the connection between two replicas with
131 $|q| \geq 0.5$ and $|q_{max}| = 0.5$ identifies the laser threshold [6]. At low pumping energy
132 0.09 mJ, Fig. 1b, only 10 connections are obtained, i.e. 0.2 % of the total of the
133 $[N_s(N_s - 1)/2]$ possible $|q|$ values. As the energy increases, the number of connections
134 increases: in Fig. 1c, at 0.19 mJ, we have 224 connections (4.5 %), at 0.50 mJ 2279
135 connections (46.0%), Fig. 1d.

136 In Fig. 1e we plot the connectivity K (black squares), that is the percentage
137 of graph edges, and $|q_{max}|$ (red circles) versus pumping energy. The laser threshold
138 corresponds to the replica symmetry breaking point $|q_{max}| = 0.5$, with $|q_{max}|$ defined
139 as the most probable $|q|$ at various pumping energy [4] and obtained from $P(q)$ as
140 demonstrated in Methods.

141 The trends in Fig. 1e show unambiguously the correspondence between the saturation
142 of the edge percentage and the RSB point, both at the laser threshold of 0.5 mJ.
143 With this results we propose the graph method as an alternative way to determine
144 RSB and RL threshold.

145 Ultrametricity

146 The hierarchical clustering of the states can be visualized by building the matrix of
147 the overlap q . In Fig. 2a,b we show the well known theoretical Parisi Ansatz [7]. In
148 the paramagnetic regime, panel a, all $q_{\alpha\beta}$ are close to 0, while in the SG, panel b, the
149 formation of clusters with $q_{\alpha\beta}$ close to 1 and -1 values is an intrinsic characteristic of
150 the system.

151 To obtain the photonic experimental counterpart we organize the 100×100 matrix
152 of overlap $q_{\alpha\beta}$, for 100 single shot measurements, by using the average linkage agglom-
153 erative clustering algorithm, details are in Methods. Three representative matrices
154 below, at and above laser threshold, in Fig. 9 of Methods, clearly show the progressive
155 cluster formation through the glass transition. For better visualization a zoom of the
156 results is reported in Fig. 2c,d. In Fig. 2d we give evidence of the cluster structure at
157 high pumping energy where the system is in the glassy regime. Contrarily, in Fig. 2c
158 at low energy the structure is flat with all overlap values close to 0.

Fig. 2 Hierarchical clustering in spin glass RL reproducing Parisi overlap Ansatz.
a,b, Theoretical Parisi Ansatz of overlap matrix in paramagnetic, non hierarchical regime (**a**) and in SG hierarchical regime (**b**). **c,d,** Overlap matrix $q_{\alpha\beta}$: at low input energy 0.09 mJ photonic analogous of paramagnetic phase (**c**); at high energy 2.07 mJ spin glass RL phase (**d**). In the matrices black pixels correspond to the self-overlap $q_{\alpha\alpha} = 0$ ($\alpha = \beta$), and the color changes from dark purple to white as q decreases. The order of the states in the experiments is given by applying the average linkage agglomerative clustering algorithm.

159 This is the first experimental spin glass Ansatz obtained directly from the analysis
 160 of the emission spectra.

161 Ultrametricity in spin glasses comes directly from the calculation of the 3-state
 162 overlap distribution $P(q_{\alpha\beta}, q_{\beta\gamma}, q_{\alpha\gamma})$. For pure states α , β and γ the 3-replica overlap
 163 distribution of spin glass phase has been calculated [3] as

$$P(q_{\alpha\beta}, q_{\beta\gamma}, q_{\alpha\gamma}) = 1/2 P(q_{\alpha\beta}) x(q_{\alpha\beta}) \delta(q_{\alpha\beta} - q_{\beta\gamma}) \delta(q_{\beta\gamma} - q_{\alpha\gamma}) \quad (3)$$

$$+ 1/2 [P(q_{\alpha\beta}) P(q_{\beta\gamma}) \theta(q_{\alpha\beta} - q_{\beta\gamma}) \delta(q_{\beta\gamma} - q_{\alpha\gamma}) + \text{permutations}]$$

164 where $\theta(x)$ is the Heaviside theta function and $x(q) = \int_{-1}^q P(q') dq'$.

165 Assuming without loss of generality that $q_{\alpha\beta} \geq q_{\beta\gamma} \geq q_{\alpha\gamma}$, Eq.(3) implies that
 166 $P(q_{\alpha\beta}, q_{\beta\gamma}, q_{\alpha\gamma})$ is nonzero only for

$$q_{\alpha\beta} \geq q_{\beta\gamma} = q_{\alpha\gamma} \quad (4)$$

167 that is the ultrametric condition for overlaps.

168 The ultrametric topology of the spin states is given by the demonstration of the
 169 ultrametric triangular inequality between their distances.

170 To this aim the Hamming distance d [35, 36] is calculated from the experiments, as
 171 $d_{\alpha\beta} = (1 - |q_{\alpha\beta}|)$ [35], for each pair of states α and β . By substituting this relation in
 172 Eq. (4) we obtain $d_{\alpha\gamma} \leq d_{\alpha\beta} = d_{\beta\gamma}$ for the distances [35, 36]. This is the ultrametric
 173 triangular inequality, that results to be intrinsic to the SG theory.

174 To demonstrate ultrametricity in our photonic SG we calculate the distribution
 175 of triangles with vertices given by three random states α, β, γ and sides $d_{\alpha\beta}, d_{\alpha\gamma},$
 176 $d_{\beta\gamma}$ [35].

177 From the experiments we obtain $[N_s(N_s - 1)(N_s - 2)]/3!$ triplets of $d_{\alpha\gamma}$, with $N_s =$
 178 100 single shot spectra. For any triplet, the Hamming distances between the states,
 179 forming three sides of a triangle, are sorted as $0 \leq d_{min} \leq d_{mid} \leq d_{max} \leq 1$. The
 180 objective is to distinguish the so-called trivial ultrametricity, in which all the triangles
 181 are equilateral, and nontrivial ultrametricity, in which a fraction of triangles is isosceles
 182 with $d_{min} \leq d_{mid} = d_{max}$.

183 In Fig. 3 we show the probability density of triangles, plotted in the plane ($d_{mid} -$
 184 $d_{min}, d_{max} - d_{mid}$) for three different energies, each point indicates a triplet forming
 185 a triangle. At low energy, in Fig. 3a, all points are grouped near the origin, which
 186 corresponds to equilateral triangles with $d_{mid} \simeq d_{min} \simeq d_{max}$. As the energy increases,
 187 the points spread towards the horizontal axis in Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c.

Fig. 3 SG ultrametricity form experimental data. a-c, Probability density of triangle side lengths, in the plane ($d_{mid} - d_{min}, d_{max} - d_{mid}$) at (a) 0.09 mJ, (b) 0.50 mJ and (c) 2.07 mJ. d, Maximum length d^* in the horizontal axis ($d_{mid} - d_{min}$) (black curve) and estimated equilateral triangles (red curve) as a function of the pumping energy.

188 To quantify the variations, in Fig. 3d we present d^* as the maximum length in the
 189 horizontal axis $d_{mid} - d_{min}$ (black curve) and the estimated percentage of equilateral

190 triangles (red curve) versus the pumping energy. The percentage is calculated as the
 191 number of points in the first 0.1×0.1 pixel of the plane, evidenced by the red square in
 192 the reported plots, over the total number of the points. Initially the maximum length
 193 in the horizontal axis d^* is close to 0.2 and the percentage of equilateral triangles is
 194 about 80%. As the energy increases, d^* rises to a saturation of about 0.8, and the
 195 percentage of equilateral triangles drops to about 20%. Both saturation trends occur
 196 at about 0.5 mJ, that is the laser threshold.

197 These results demonstrate that more isosceles triangles are formed with two sides
 198 $d_{mid} \simeq d_{max}$ and larger than the third one d_{min} and give the first experimental prove
 199 of ultrametricity in spin glasses.

200 Topological Energy Landscape

201 In the previous paragraph the hierarchical cluster structure and the ultrametric archi-
 202 tecture of spin glass replicas have been evidenced. Here, we obtain the topology of the
 203 SG energy landscape directly from the clustering of the photonic spin states.

204 Different representations of the energy landscape have been reported in literature.
 205 They include funnels, clusters of minima, tendrils, disconnective graphs and are widely
 206 used in the fields of chemistry and biology [37, 38]. They describe the general shape
 207 and overall connectivity that characterize rugged energy surfaces.

208 An open experimental challenge is achieving a direct measurement of the topology
 209 of the replica landscape.

210 Rugged funnel shapes of phase space energy landscape in spin glass systems have
 211 been numerically obtained, where a hierarchical structure of energy scales is found at
 212 the different levels of the barrier tree, with a single long branch (the global minimum)
 213 and many shorter branches separating from it [39–41]. Hierarchical clustering leads
 214 to hierarchical energy landscape. The local minima in the non-hierarchical clustering
 215 system result from the original zero energy mode of the classical energy Hamiltonian
 216 and the energy minima are clustered into different branches, following the topology
 217 of the replica distances.

218 The average linkage agglomerative clustering algorithm, used in the previous
 219 section and described in Methods paragraph, furnishes a tree-like structure of all the
 220 the distances $d_{\alpha\beta}$ between spin states called dendrogram. We depict in Fig. 4a-c three
 221 examples for three different input energies showing the complex structure below, at
 222 and above the laser threshold. The ordering of the branches of the tree provides a nat-
 223 ural ordering of the states. Longer branches correspond to larger distances between
 224 the connecting points. The reported results clearly illustrate the gradual occurrence
 225 of hierarchical relationship between the states from the paramagnetic regime, Fig. 4a
 226 towards the random laser SG phase, Fig. 4c. At threshold, Fig. 4b, replicas start to
 227 form the first large clusters.

228 In Fig. 4d-f we report the measured energy landscape from the distance dendro-
 229 grams of Fig. 4a-c, considering the energy barrier values proportional to the distances.
 230 Details are described in Methods section. For low pumping energy, Fig. 4d, the clus-
 231 tering dendrogram gives a flat non hierarchical energy landscape and, as the input
 232 pumping increases, the landscape shows a rugged funnel-type topology as expected

Fig. 4 Experimental energy landscape representation across the phase transition. **a-c** Distance $d_{\alpha\gamma}$ dendrograms below, at and above the RL threshold. Dendrograms are calculated by sorting the Hamming distance of the states from the experiments with the average linkage agglomerative clustering algorithm. **d-f** Energy landscape profiles obtained directly from the clustering dendrograms of the left panel, respectively. See Methods for details. Input energy is 0.9 mJ (**a,d**); 0.5 mJ (**b,e**); 2.07 mJ (**c,f**)

233 for spin glass systems, Fig. 4e and Fig. 4f. Barriers and local minima are evident in
 234 the high energy glassy regime, Fig. 4f.

235 To the best of our knowledge this is the first experimental energy landscape rep-
 236 resentation of a complex SG system. Fig. 4 unambiguously shows the transition from
 237 ergodic to non ergodic by changing a measurable physical system, emblematic of
 238 theoretical spin ensemble.

239 Conclusions

240 In this work we used random laser emission to demonstrate the ultrametric nature of
 241 the spin glass states. We present a new approach for the investigation of the replica
 242 symmetry breaking based on the graph representation of the overlap parameter and
 243 we measure the profile of the energy landscape from the experimental SG overlaps.

244 Spin glass theories are the foundation of complex systems and Parisi replica trick
 245 is a fundamental paradigm: the many metastable states of a glass are treated as
 246 replicas and the overlap between replicas is identified as the order parameter. The
 247 distribution of the overlap defines the thermodynamics of the complex system. In out
 248 of equilibrium glassy regime such distribution has a hierarchical ultrametric structure
 249 and it is signature of the breaking of the replica symmetry.

250 This fascinating and universal theory lacks of a direct experimental proof.

251 Random lasers offer the great advantage of measuring the overlap parameter
252 directly from emission spectra and thus are known to be excellent examples of SGs.

253 In our experiments we measure the distance between the replicas from the overlap,
254 we obtain the equivalent of the Parisi Ansatz showing the clustering of the states and
255 we attain the topology of the complex energy landscape through the phase transition.
256 In the ordered paramagnetic regime one large basin is obtained and above threshold
257 in the disordered phase many metastable minima emerge.

258 The most relevant result is the first experimental evidence of ultrametricity in
259 spin glasses. We demonstrate it by measuring the distribution of the replica triplets
260 forming isosceles and equilateral triangles. This is the only way to assess the topology
261 of the replica space and it has been reported only in numerical simulations.

262 Here, we show the increase of the number of isosceles triangles and the decrease
263 of the equilateral ones at high energy as an unambiguous signature of the ultrametric
264 landscape of the states in the glassy regime.

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376 **Methods**

377 **Sample preparation and characterization.**

378 Silica xerogel powders were obtained by sol-gel synthesis performed at room temper-
379 ature.

380 Silica sol-gel synthesis was performed by the controlled hydrolysis of the alkoxide
381 tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), followed by hydrolysis and condensation reactions in
382 an aqueous solution. In this work, the synthesis was acid-catalyzed by the addition of
383 nitric acid. At low pH levels, silica tends to form linear molecules that are occasionally
384 cross-linked. These molecular chains become entangled and form additional branches,
385 resulting in gelation [42]. Initially 5.5 mL of TEOS and 8.5 mL of ethanol- Rhodamine
386 6G solution at 10^{-3} mol/L are mixed. This solution stays under constant agitation
387 for approximately 15 minutes. Then 5.5 mL of deionized water, 0.15 mL of nitric acid
388 and 1.9 mL of dimethylformamide are added into the initial solution. The system is
389 kept under stirring at room temperature for about 10 minutes for homogenization
390 and formation of the initial sol. The sol is placed in drying oven (50 °C) for two days,
391 resulting in a dry silica xerogel.

392 The xerogel is then heat treated at 100 °C for 1 hour to remove the remaining
393 solvents. Then, the solid material is minced using a mortar and pestle to obtain a
394 homogeneous powder, that is carefully deposited in a sample chamber made of two

Fig. 5 Sample preparation and characterization. **a**, Sol-Gel process and sample preparation. **b**, Powder morphology by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Inset: Size distribution of the powder grains.

395 microscope slides sealed by double-sided tape with a thickness of 250 μm . Fig. 5a
 396 summarizes the Sol-Gel process and sample preparation and Fig. 5b shows the
 397 powder morphology by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The powder presents a
 398 polydisperse particle size distribution, with an average size of about 5 μm , it is possi-
 399 ble to observe a fraction of larger particles, with dimensions up to 20 μm (top inset).
 400

401 RL experiments

402 **RL setup.** A sketch of the optical setup is reported in Fig. 6.

403 The sample is pumped by a Continuum-Surelite frequency doubled Q-switched
 404 Nd:YAG pulsed laser emitting at $\lambda = 532 \text{ nm}$, with 10 Hz repetition rate, 6 ns pulse
 405 duration. The pumping beam is focused on the sample by a microscope objective
 406 with numerical aperture of 0.55 and we use an illuminated area of about 500 μm
 407 of diameter. The scattered light emitted from the sample is collected from its front
 408 surface and focused into an optic fiber connected to a Andor Shamrock SR-303i-A
 409 spectrometer with a Czerny-Turner arrangement, 303 mm focal length and diffraction
 410 grating density of 1200 grooves/mm, equipped with electrically cooled iDus camera
 411 detector.

412 The acquisition is triggered by the pump laser flash lamp at 10Hz repetition rate.
 413 The sample is pumped perpendicularly along the z direction and all reported spectra
 414 are taken from single pumping shots. A notch filter is positioned at the entrance of
 415 the fiber to remove the residual incident laser beam.

416 **RL measurements.** We illustrate in Fig. 7a-c, emissions of subsequent 100 shots
 417 taken at 0.09 mJ, 0.50 mJ and 2.07 mJ, respectively. The spectra are characterized
 418 by a broad line emission, typical for Rhodamine 6G molecules at low energy, Fig. 7a.

419 As the pumping energy increases, random laser line width reduction is observed as
 420 shown in Fig. 7b and 7c. The absence of spikes in the emission spectra is characteris-
 421 tic of non-resonant feedback in which light propagates in a diffusive regime. Moreover,
 422 the growth of spectral fluctuations with increasing pumping is evident.

Fig. 6 Scheme of the random laser setup.

Fig. 7 Replica symmetry breaking from $P(q)$. **a-c**, Three representative series of emission spectra (100 shots) at various input energy. **d-f**, Overlap distribution $P(q)$ at 0.09 mJ, 0.50 mJ and 2.07 mJ respectively.

423 The replica symmetry breaking behaviour results are shown in Fig. 7d-f. We
 424 present three examples of the overlap distribution $P(q)$. At low pumping energy
 425 (Fig. 7d), most of the overlaps q are centered around the zero value, meaning that the
 426 emitted modes weakly interact. As the energy increases, the modes are coupled by
 427 the nonlinearity and q assumes all possible values in the range $[-1,1]$. Such behavior
 428 characterizes the breaking of the replica symmetry.

429 Fig. 8a shows the growth of the mean intensity $\sum_{\lambda=1}^N \bar{I}(\lambda)/N$ over replicas and
 430 wavelength (black curve) and the respective variance (red curve) for increasing input
 431 energy. In both curves a threshold from the spontaneous regime to stimulated emission
 432 at 0.5 mJ input energy is observed.

Fig. 8 RL Threshold characterization. **a**, Mean emission intensity (black curve) and variance (red curve) vs pumping energy. **b**, $|q_{\max}|$ (black curve) and FWHM (red curve) vs pumping energy.

433 In Fig. 8b the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the emission band (red
 434 curve) and the $|q_{\max}|$ (black curve) as a function of the input energy are depicted.
 435 $|q_{\max}|$ is the absolute value of the most probable overlap q [4]. Bandwidth narrowing
 436 from about 50 nm to about 25 nm (reduction of 50%) and a clear transition from
 437 $|q_{\max}| \simeq 0$ to $|q_{\max}| \simeq 1$ at 0.50 mJ are evidenced.

439 Linkage agglomerative clustering algorithm

440 The linkage agglomerative clustering algorithm begins with a forest of clusters and
 441 each state belongs to its own cluster. When two closest clusters s and t are combined
 442 into a single cluster u , they are removed from the forest, and u is added to the forest.
 443 The distance between two clusters is the average distance between all pairs of members
 444 of the clusters. This process continues, with the definition of inter-cluster distances
 445 given by the average of all the distances between elements of each cluster. When only
 446 one cluster remains in the forest, the algorithm stops, and this cluster becomes the
 447 root. At each interaction, the algorithm must update the distance matrix to reflect the
 448 distance of the newly formed cluster u with the remaining clusters in the forest [43, 44].

449 We apply this algorithm to obtain the overlap matrices reported in Fig. 9, where
 450 the progressive cluster formation through the RL threshold (0,5 mJ) is demonstrated,
 451 as the first experimental example of the Parisi Ansatz.

452 Energy landscape construction

453 We construct the schematic energy landscape based on the distance dendrogram,
 454 considering that the energy barrier values are proportional to the distance $d_{\alpha\beta}$ between
 455 replicas and d_{st} between the generated clusters.

Fig. 9 Hierarchical clustering. 100×100 matrix of overlap q , for 100 single shot measurements, obtained by using the average linkage agglomerative clustering algorithm, at different input energy of 0.09 mJ: below threshold (a), 0.50 mJ: at threshold (b) and 2.07 mJ: above threshold (c).

Fig. 10 Energy landscape from dendrogram. **a**, Dendrogram at input energy 2.07 mJ, the same of Fig. 4, and correspondent array of lines with position at each end point of the dendrogram and height equal to the respective height in the dendrogram. Here each line is a gaussian curve with width w^* . **b**, Same as panel **a** with gaussian width $w = 20w^*$. This is the one we consider as the topological energy landscape of the glassy RL.

456 We show the procedure in Fig. 10 for the dendrogram obtained at 2.07 mJ injected
 457 energy, as an example.

458 We position on the horizontal axis of the energy landscape representation all the
 459 end points in the dendrogram and keeping the same order, as shown in Fig. 10a.
 460 Then, gaussian curves are generated centered on each horizontal coordinate and with
 461 amplitude equal to the correspondent branch length (vertical coordinate). Their width

462 w is variable and we indicate w^* as the smallest significant width. The sum of the
463 gaussian funnels gives the energy landscape profile.

464 When w is small, the individual gaussians are narrower and have less overlap.
465 This results in sharper and more separate peaks in the sum, as depicted in Fig. 10a
466 where $w = w^*$. As the width increases, Fig. 10b, the gaussian funnels begin to overlap
467 more significantly, creating a smoother and more continuous sum, where the cluster
468 structure emerges. The generated image is filled with a color map showing the variation
469 in amplitude (distance in the dendrogram).

470 In this work we choose $w = 20 w^*$, Fig. 10b and Fig. 4d-f, that furnishes a good
471 clustering degree to properly evidence a topology with valleys and barriers of the
472 glassy state.

473 Acknowledgements

474 This publication was produced thanks to funding under the bilateral agreement
475 CNR/FAPESP (Brazil), "Machine learning for Random characterization and phase
476 retrieval", two-year period 2023-2024, grant CUP B83C24000660005 (Italy) and grant
477 2023/08033-7 (Brazil), and the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível
478 Superior – Brazil (CAPES) – Finance Code 001, by CNPQ through the National
479 Institute of Photonics (INCT) program.

480 S.F. and N.G. acknowledge Project ECS 0000024 Rome Technopole, – CUP
481 B83C22002890005, NRP Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.5, Funded by the Euro-
482 pean Union – NextGenerationEU, the results will be used for training and formation
483 of students.

484 C. C. acknowledges Project ECS 0000024 Rome Technopole - CUP B83C22002890006,
485 NRP Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.5, Funded by the European Union
486 - NextGenerationEU and HORIZON EIC-2022-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01
487 HEISINGBERG Project 101114978.

488 We are thankful to Mr. Deen Islam and Dr. Andrea Gnoli for technical support in
489 laboratory.